

Examining the Efficacy of Adopting, Implementing and Sustaining Discrete Trial Training Program for Developing Social Communication Skills in a Case with Autism Spectrum Disorder: District Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab Province, Pakistan

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Abstract

This research paper has examined the efficacy of adopting, implementing and sustaining the DTT program for developing social communication skills in a case with an autism spectrum disorder in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan. The researchers obtained the face and content validity of the self-made research instrument and DTT data recording sheets by five experts. Five steps were performed to carry out the necessities of the study and therefore meet the aim of the study. Visual analysis under Nugent Method was performed to investigate the skill development rate of change across all the treatment phases. It was found that the task objectives were developed at a higher rate of change during phase E.

Introduction

Applied behavior analysts work to develop communication among individuals with ASD with Autism spectrum disorders (ASD). Multiple intervention strategies play a significant role in building appropriate social behavior (s) among individuals with ASD. Discrete Trial Training (DTT) is one of the structured types of Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA). B.F Skinner documented it in 1957 (Sundberg and Partington, 1999). The ABA investigates human interactions with their environment over time and develops intervention strategies to reduce the decline in the misconduct of social behavior among individuals with ASD (Ryan et al., 2011).

The ABA strategy discussed in the current paper focused on serving individuals with ASD by developing intended skills in small, measurable components (Smith, 2001). It is worthy to note that DTT is not the only ABA component used by behavior analysts to teach different skills among individuals with ASD. Contrary to this, multiple methods that fall under the umbrella of ABA are often used by these specialists to aid individuals with ASD (Ghezzi, 2007). Additionally, some health care professional trainers do DTT combined with other strategies fell under the umbrella of ABA. This research paper aimed to examine the efficacy of adopting, implementing and sustaining the DTT program for developing social communication skills in a case with an autism spectrum disorder in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan.

Literature review

The usefulness of ABA Programs

Ivar Lovaas first investigated ABA programs' usefulness among individuals with ASD (Ryan et al., 2011). Lovaas believed that DTT features were significant in developing social skills among individuals with ASD (Weiss, 2005). DTT has worked well for developing social skills that need to be repeated, e.g., building imitation skills, receptive skills and academic skills. DTT has also performed effectively for teaching skills that are not naturally encouraging. DTT allows maximum opportunities for the individual with ASD and the professional trainers to present many learning trials in a session, thus increasing the exposure of learning the intended skill (Sundberg & Partington, 1999).

It also casts doubt on the ability of individuals with ASD to generalize the learned skill and whether an individual with ASD learns to initiate social communication appropriately or not. Specifically, DTT as a structured strategy is usable with sequential responses taught to individuals with ASD. When the individual with ASD is first taught the correct answer in the predetermined learning sequence, some answers can be learned with motivation. Finally, after awarding the reinforcement, the answer the professional trainer and / or instructor wants is strengthened, ultimately bringing positive effect or intent in the targeted behavior (Smith, 2001).

The essence of Discrete Trial Training

For example, the instructor, e.g., can bring a list of three cards in the listening language function. The instructor requests the individual with ASD “touch the card of a cat.” If the individual with ASD answers positively, the individual with ASD is allowed to access the favorite toy. If the individual with ASD answers negatively, the instructor corrects the individual with ASD by physically causing them to touch the card of a cat. At the same time, the instructor says, “that is the card of a cat.” The instructor reintroduces the chain of learning trials until the individual with ASD answers well. If the individual with ASD answers incorrectly or does not answer, the instructor corrects the error. Therefore, the instructor makes a direct response from the individual with ASD. The instructor needs to know the use of motivating prompt hierarchies while implementing the structured procedure of DTT. The instructor should consistently utilize the least interrupted prompt to find the best answer (Smith, 2001).

Dynamic Hierarchies of Prompt

There are two different ways of implementing dynamic hierarchies of prompt in DTT. The first is the most to least hierarchy of prompt, e.g., physical prompt, slight prompt and gestural prompt. The second is the least to the most hierarchy of prompts, e.g., gestural, slight, and physical prompts. Using prompt hierarchies is essential for individuals with ASD in learning a skill. Still, an instructor must note when the individual with ASD does not become overwhelmed by the reinforcement. The instructor may become exhausted by gradually increasing the delay between the introduction of the incentive and the appreciation and reduction of prompt properties related to length and stiffness (Ghezzi, 2007).

Effective Reinforcement to Support an Autonomous Response

DTT as a structured intervention emphasizes making and presenting learning opportunities for the individual with ASD by using tangible and measurable targets that the individual with ASD achieves at different response rates. Once the instructor has given the intended answer, they must provide it promptly to reinforce the difference. By providing reinforcement, the instructor strengthens the probability that the intended behavior or response occurs again and again. Effective reinforcement lets the instructor know which works best to achieve the goal. Well, different types of reinforcements can also be used. When strengthening the intended behavior, the instructor can increase the level of intensity of the reinforcement to support the autonomous response (Ghezzi, 2007).

Effectiveness of Discrete Trial Training

The ABA method makes ensure that the individual with ASD learns in a non-disruptive environment while working individually with the professional trainer and instructor. Overall, DTT specified components and its implementation protocols make it highly structured. Behavior analysts differ on whether the highly structured protocols used in DTT make it easy or very strenuous to use in multiple settings with this heterogeneous group of symptoms (Ghezzi, 2007).

DTT has been shown to increase understanding skills, language skills, academic skills, social skills and others (Ryan et al., 2011). DTT is considered the best-studied method to develop the following targets imitation skills, language skills, communication skills, conversation skills, and grammar and syntax skills” (Smith, 2001). Weiss (2005) believed that DTT forms the basis of touching, requesting, imitation, receptive language skills, and teaching skills that are not naturally motivating. In addition, Ryan et al. (2011) favored that DTT has a wealth of research that supports its use in educating individuals with ASD. Delprato et al. (2001) found by comparing many different studies that the structures procedures of DTT are more effective in the acquisition of different skills in individuals with ASD.

Jennet et al. (2008) compared DTT versus request model to teach requests among individuals with ASD. The researchers used the language program with the two teaching methods and matched the results in the study. He found that participants in his DTT study, on average, had more eye contact when trained with DTT than when trained with the request model. He noted that the advantage of using DTT is that the individual with ASD is exposed to many temptations and may therefore learn to ask for many different things. More importantly, parents of individuals with ASD involved in the study noted that four out of six participants increased automatic eye contact, which showed that the intervention was successful in teaching the intended skills.

Hume et al. (2005) examined a group of one hundred and ninety-five parents with four individuals with ASD from two to eight years of age to assess the services available to young individuals with ASD and their families. The study included questions about the family population, types and number of interventions used, strategies and study areas tested, settings, applied intervention tests, service delivery tests and results of the interventions used. The results revealed that twenty-six percent of the families surveyed were used separate experimental training with their individual with ASD on average sixteen hours per week, which were very high the number of hours spent on any of the interventions tested. In addition, research has found the following services provided direct and effective support for their entire individual with ASD development: speech therapy with seventy-six percent, sensory integration with sixty-nine percent, discrete trial training with sixty-eight percent and social support with sixty-seven percent (Hume et al., 2005). Only seven percent of Parents revealed disagreement regarding the use of DTT as an effective intervention in the growth and development of their

individual with ASD. On the other hand, Tissot and Evans (2003) investigated the effectiveness of visual teaching strategies for individuals with ASD. However, Harrower and Dunlap (2001) explained the participation of individuals with ASD in general education classrooms to learn social skills.

Jones et al. (2007) focused on very young individuals with ASD and extended behavioral interventions to deal with automated communication. In addition, the study was conducted across the early age individuals with ASD and taught spontaneous responses using multiple interventions, including DTT using specific requests.

Methodology

Population

Individuals with ASD in govt. special education centers across the Punjab province of Pakistan were the study's population.

Participant

PE (a pseudonym) was enrolled at Govt. Special Education Centre, Gojra. He was a boy of six years and eleven months old. He was an early childhood boy with ASD. His order in siblings was fourth. He had one sibling with a disability in the family. He belonged to a working social class with a family income of fifteen thousand per month. His religion was Islam.

He was a minimal-verbal individual with ASD with an autism spectrum disorder. He required substantial support (level 2 of severity) based on the diagnostic criteria of DSM-5 for the autism spectrum disorder. Her symptoms associated with autism spectrum disorder were present in the early developmental period. These symptoms were causing difficulties in his daily functioning. He had persistent deficits in social communication and non-verbal communication and had restricted/stereotyped behaviors observed on the diagnostic criteria of DSM-5 for the autism spectrum disorder.

He had deficits in social communication with a total score of 41 and non-verbal communication with a total score of 15 measured on the autism diagnostic interview (ADI-R). He had restricted/stereotyped behaviors with a total score of 5 and abnormal developmental patterns at or before 6 months with a total score of 3 measured on the autism diagnostic interview (ADI-R).

He had mild to moderate severity for the autism spectrum disorder with a T-score of 65 measured on the social responsiveness scale (SRS-2). He had an I.Q score of 63 (low average) measured on WISC-V. He obtained a total score of 13 on the non-verbal index and 40 on the general ability index. His mental age was of four years old individual with ASD.

PE had deficits associated with an autism spectrum disorder. Still, the core areas of deficit were investigated using a self-developed tool based on DSM-5 and validated by experts with Cronbach's alpha value of 0.875. Based on it, sub-core areas of deficits were formulated and later task analysis was performed across each task objective.

Research Method

A quantitative research method was employed to conduct the study. This method focuses on data that can be measured and effectively answers "how" and "what" across the given phenomenon to be investigated. In such a method, direct and quantifiable questions often contain phrases such as what percentage, what proportion, to what extent, how many, how much (Goertzen, 2017). Therefore, the quantitative method supported the researchers in answering the study's formulated research questions.

Research Design

The researchers selected the experimental research design, precisely a single-subject experimental design, to conduct the present study. Therefore, the phenomenon was experimented with based on a single-subject study design across five participants. Single subject study design rigorously evaluates intervention efficacy with one or a small number of chosen cases (Morgan & Morgan, 2008).

Table 1

Conditions across Phases in which PE was Required to Respond

Phases	Description
A	Baseline (investigating initial proficiency level)
B	Administering treatment inside the psychologist room under regressive inter-trial interval technique along with priming sessions technique in addition to no error correction/signaling no technique (participant with researchers)
C	Administering treatment inside the psychologist room under progressive inter-trial interval technique along with priming sessions technique in addition to error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (participant with researchers)
D	Administering treatment inside the autism-friendly training room under regressive inter-trial interval technique along with priming sessions technique in addition to no error

E	correction/signaling no technique (participant with researchers) Administering treatment inside the autism-friendly training room under progressive inter-trial interval technique along with priming sessions technique in addition to error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (participant with researchers)
A	Return to baseline (withdrawing treatment conditions) (participant with researchers)
Follow up 1 (appropriateness)	Investigating appropriateness of the skill under novel stimuli (participant with researchers)
Follow up 2 (generalization)	Generalization of the skill (participant with the class teacher)

Note. This table shows conditions across phases in which PE was required to respond.

Instrumentation

The researchers obtained the face and content validity of the self-made research instrument and DTT data recording sheets by five experts. Research instruments were sent to experts through the mail. Later, pieces of advice given by the experts through the mail were incorporated to make the research instruments valid to collect data and therefore reach the study results. Hina-Hina Rating Scale for the Identification of Core Areas of Social Communication Deficits of Individuals with ASD with Autism Spectrum Disorder reserved 8.75 Cronbach's alpha value of reliability. The detail of each research instrument is given below:

1. The researchers developed a Hina-Hina Rating Scale for the Identification of Core Areas of Social Communication Deficits of Individual with ASD with Autism Spectrum Disorder (HH-RSICSCDASD) based on the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5, 2013)* to identify social communication deficits of individuals with ASD which was validated by five experts. This instrument was consisted of two parts. The first part contained demographic information and the second part contained specific information to identify social communication skills of individuals with ASD on a five-point Likert scale.
2. The researchers designed DTT baseline data sheets based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by National Professional Development Center on Autism Spectrum Disorders (NPDCASD) in 2010' to collect baseline data. This instrument validated by five experts included two parts: presenting antecedents and obtaining responses under two dimensions. The task was performed with an initial proficiency level in percentage and occurrence of interfering behavior.
3. The researchers designed DTT treatment data sheets based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by NPDCASD in 2010' to collect treatment data and validate it by five experts. This instrument validated by five experts was based on five steps of DTT such as instruction, prompt, response, consequence and intertribal interval. Each response was measured on a three-point Likert scale, and task performed with mastery level in percentage was observed.
4. The researchers designed DTT return to baseline data sheets based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by NPDCASD in 2010' to collect return to baseline data and validated by five experts. Five experts validated this instrument included two parts: presenting antecedents and obtaining responses under two dimensions. The task was performed with an initial proficiency level in percentage and occurrence of interfering behavior.
5. The researchers designed DTT's first follow-up data sheets based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by NPDCASD in 2010' to collect follow-up data. This instrument validated by five experts included two parts: presenting antecedents and obtaining responses under two dimensions. The task was performed with an initial proficiency level in percentage and occurrence of interfering behavior.
6. The researchers designed DTT's second follow-up data sheet based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by NPDCASD in 2010' to collect follow-up data. This instrument validated by five experts included two parts: presenting antecedents and obtaining responses under two dimensions. The task was performed with an initial proficiency level in percentage and occurrence of interfering behavior.
7. The researchers designed DTT mastery sheets based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by NPDCASD in 2010'. This instrument validated by five experts was included task and proficiency level under 10% to 100% to be observed across each trial under each experimental session (ES).

8. The researchers designed DTT implementation sheets based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by NPDCASD in 2010'. This instrument validated by five experts has included stepwise execution of the DTT program to be observed across each trial under each ES.
9. The researchers used the Partial Interval Recording Scale to conduct a Brief Stimulus Preference Assessment (BSPA)/Free Operant Assessment (FOA).

Procedures

At first, the researchers developed a parent consent form to take the willingness of the parents for their individual with ASD to take part in the study. In this way, the researchers obtained consent from the parents and teacher to participate in the diagnosed segment with ASD confirmed in the study.

Second, the researchers developed a teacher consent form to take the willingness of the teacher for their individual with ASD to take part in the study. In this way, the researchers obtained consent from the teacher to participate in the diagnosed segment with ASD confirmed in the study.

Consequently, upon that, it was assured to the parents and teacher that there would be no harm during implementing discrete trials. Furthermore, it was assured to the parents and teachers that their names and other information related to their consent would be kept confidential and used for the current research. In this way, five participants diagnosed with ASD were chosen to intervene under the formulated design of the DTT program.

A third, the researchers developed a permission granted letter for the headmistress to conduct a study at Govt. Special Education Centre, Gojra (GSECG), Toba Tek Singh. Consequent to that, the researchers got permission from the headmistress of the GSECG, Toba Tek Singh, to start the experiment upon the chosen participants of the study. An experiment was held during the timings of the GSECG, Toba Tek Singh. In this way, the researchers fulfilled the research ethics to run the study there.

Before collecting baseline data, the researchers selected core areas of social communication deficits (CASCD) by using a self-developed Rating Scale to identify the Social Communication Skills of Individuals with ASD. The class teacher to identify social communication deficits. Here, the researchers put the obtained data into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and the descriptive statistics helped investigate the CASCD. It enabled the researchers to formulate the sub CASCD under each statistically obtained CASCD. Based on each sub CASCD, the researchers thence set the final task objectives sheet to be taught under the set criteria of mastery output (MO). Each of the target stimuli was then presented without distracter stimuli within the formulated sessions of DTT program to reach the study results. The researchers broke each task objective down and prepared steps for lesson progression. The researchers worked on the cue sheet, Least to Most Hierarchical Prompt Level Sheet, Most to Least Hierarchical Reinforcement Level Sheet and set materials to deliver the trials. Later, the researchers prepared a context sheet to carry the research out and reach the results.

At fifth, the researchers selected preferred tangible positive reinforcers to pair with the target skills before obtaining response measurements. Therefore, the researchers selected positive reinforcers to develop social communication skills. It was important to note that the type of reinforcer depended upon the individual and the situation. Each reinforcer may have the same and/or different effect on each of the chosen individual with ASD of the study. As the direct preference assessment techniques are the most valid means of identifying potential reinforcers stated by Hagopian et al. (2004), selecting with several items Rush et al. (2010), at least two tangible items to pair with the target skill follow the brief stimulus preference assessment (BSPA)/free operant assessment (FOA) defined by (Roane et al., 1998) to identify highly motivating preferred tangible positive reinforcers, ultimately work the best to develop social communication skills for each of the chosen individual with ASD of the study.

At sixth, the researchers calculated total ESs to be observed. PE observed three ESs each day with mastery criterion set at 90% correct independent response during three consecutive one-on-one instructional discrete trials. Each ES was spreading over fifteen minutes of duration for each of the chosen participants of the study. In this way, PE observed 45 hours and 2700 minutes to develop social communication skills during the two months of training.

In the seventh step, obtained data were visually analyzed under the "Nugent" method (Engel & Schutt, 2013).

Results

Examining the Efficacy of Adopting, Implementing and Sustaining Discrete Trial Training Program for Developing PSS across ESs and Follow up Periods

Note. This figure assessed change by plotting L, T, V.

- ^aAC=0.00 (NCR), PC=0.00%, RC=0.0, RLS=0.0 to 0.0 (NCR)
- ^bAC=15 (NCR), PC=1.25%, RC=1.3636, RLS=12 to 27 (NCR)
- ^cAC=14 (NCR), PC=1.0769%, RC=1.0769, RLS=13 to 27 (NCR)
- ^dAC=13 (NCR), PC=0.9285%, RC=0.8666, RLS=14 to 27 (NCR)
- ^eAC=21 (NCR), PC=3.5%, RC=2.1, RLS=6 to 27 (NCR)
- ^aAC=-1 (NCR), PC=-0.1666%, RC=-0.1111, RLS=6 to 5 (NCR)
- ^{f1}AC=-1 (NCR), PC=-0.25%, RC=-0.1111, RLS=4 to 3 (NCR)
- ^{f2}AC=-3 (NCR), PC=-1%, RC=-0.3333, RLS=3 to 0 (NCR)

Examining the Efficacy of Adopting, Implementing and Sustaining Discrete Trial Training Program for Developing CPVL across ESs and Follow up Periods

Note. This figure assessed change by plotting L, T, V.

- ^aAC=0.00 (NCR), PC=0.00%, RC=0.0, RLS=0.0 to 0.0 (NCR)
- ^bAC=15 (NCR), PC=1.25%, RC=1.0714, RLS=12 to 27 (NCR)
- ^cAC=25 (NCR), PC=12.5%, RC=1.2727, RLS=2 to 27 (NCR)
- ^dAC=11 (NCR), PC=0.6875%, RC=0.9166, RLS=16 to 27 (NCR)
- ^eAC=14 (NCR), PC=1.0769%, RC=2.2727, RLS=13 to 27 (NCR)
- ^aAC=2 (NCR), PC=0.5%, RC=0.2222, RLS=4 to 6 (NCR)
- ^{f1}AC=-1 (NCR), PC=-0.3333%, RC=-0.1111, RLS=3 to 2 (NCR)
- ^{f2}AC=-3 (NCR), PC=-1%, RC=-0.3333, RLS=3 to 0 (NCR)

Examining the Efficacy of Adopting, Implementing and Sustaining Discrete Trial Training Program for Developing CPRVL across ESs and Follow up Periods

Sessions

Note. This figure assessed change by plotting L, T, V.

^aAC=0.00 (NCR), PC=0.00%, RC=0.0, RLS=0.0 to 0.0 (NCR)

^bAC=19 (NCR), PC=2.375%, RC=1.4615, RLS=8 to 27 (NCR)

^cAC=25 (NCR), PC=12.5%, RC=1, RLS=2 to 27 (NCR)

^dAC=15 (NCR), PC=1.25%, RC=1.0714, RLS=12 to 27 (NCR)

^eAC=13 (NCR), PC=0.9285%, RC=1.923, RLS=14 to 27 (NCR)

^aAC=-4 (NCR), PC=-0.6666%, RC=-0.4444, RLS=6 to 2 (NCR)

^{f1}AC=-1 (NCR), PC=-0.25%, RC=-0.1111, RLS=4 to 3 (NCR)

^{f2}AC=-2 (NCR), PC=-0.5%, RC=-0.2222, RLS=4 to 2 (NCR)

Examining the Efficacy of Adopting, Implementing and Sustaining Discrete Trial Training Program for Developing CPRVR across ESs and Follow up Periods

Sessions

Note. This figure assessed change by plotting L, T, V.

^aAC=0.00 (NCR), PC=0.00%, RC=0.0, RLS=0.0 to 0.0 (NCR)

^bAC=15 (NCR), PC=1.25%, RC=1.3636, RLS=12 to 27 (NCR)

^cAC=11 (NCR), PC=0.6875%, RC=1.1666, RLS=16 to 27 (NCR)

^dAC=13 (NCR), PC=0.9285%, RC=1.4444, RLS=14 to 27 (NCR)

^eAC=7 (NCR), PC=0.35%, RC=1.5714, RLS=20 to 27 (NCR)

^aAC=0.0 (NCR), PC=0.0%, RC=0.0, RLS=6 to 6 (NCR)

^{f1}AC=-4 (NCR), PC=-0.6666%, RC=-0.4444, RLS=6 to 2 (NCR)

^{f2}AC=-1 (NCR), PC=-0.3333%, RC=-0.1111, RLS=3 to 2 (NCR)

Discussion

The researchers assessed change by plotting L, T, V over each step of TA of each EP and detected AC, PC and finally RC over an overall trend line of each EP for PSS. The trend of progress shows inconsistency throughout the phases, with an ascending or descending order of CR across the ESs. Such irregular patterns explain the random rate of CR for PE over achieving the skill of PSS. It also identifies that phase E reserves a low level of change in variability for MO as compared to phase B, phase C and phase D. Furthermore, the four distinctive decreases in PE's slopes of progress were observed across 2nd and 4th and finally 9thES of phase D. It is reflective of the characteristics of individuals with ASD, where once they are provided with the routine based repetitive strategy and practice to perform the skill, they eventually master it. Additionally, the slopes of progress in phase E generally show fewer fluctuations around the mean slop FMS than phase B, phase C and phase D. Hamdan (2018) proposed a training program based on discrete trial training to improve non-verbal communication skills children with an autism spectrum disorder.

The researchers assessed change by plotting L, T, V over each step of TA of each EP and detected AC, PC and finally RC over an overall trend line of each EP for CPVL. The trend of progress shows inconsistency throughout the phases, with an ascending or descending order of CR across the ESs. Such irregular patterns explain the random rate of CR for PE over achieving the skill of CPVL. It also identifies that phase E reserves a low level of change in variability for MO as compared to phase B, phase C and phase D. Furthermore, the four distinctive decreases in PE's slopes of progress were observed across 2nd and 6thES of phase D. It is reflective of the characteristics of individuals with ASD, where once they are provided with the routine based repetitive strategy and practice to perform the skill, they eventually master it. Additionally, the slopes of progress in phase E generally show fewer fluctuations around the mean slop FMS as compared to phase B, phase C and phase D. Likewise, May et al. (2011) investigated the effects of a prompt stimulus display on therapists' accuracy, rate, and variation of trial type delivery during discrete trial teaching.

The researchers assessed change by plotting L, T, V over each step of TA of each EP and detected AC, PC and finally RC over an overall trend line of each EP for CPRVL. The trend of progress shows inconsistency throughout the phases, with an ascending or descending order of CR across the ESs. Such irregular patterns explain the random rate of CR for PE over achieving the skill of CPRVL. It also identifies that phase E reserves a low level of change in variability for MO compared to phase B, phase C, and phase D. Furthermore, the four distinctive decreases in PE's slopes of progress were observed across the 4th and 9th ES of phase B. It reflects the characteristics of individuals with ASD, where once they are provided with the routine-based repetitive strategy and practice to perform the skill, they eventually master it. Additionally, the slopes of progress in phase E generally show less fluctuations around the mean slop FMS as compared to phase B, phase C and phase D. Discrete trial training is a well-established intervention for developing verbal and non-verbal communication skills to children with autism spectrum disorder. However, few published guidelines are available for determining whether a child's rate of learning a specific skill is satisfactory, and what to do if not (Ferraioli et al., 2005).

The researchers assessed change by plotting L, T, V over each step of TA of each EP and detected AC, PC and finally RC over an overall trend line of each EP for CPRVR. The trend of progress shows inconsistency throughout the phases, with an ascending or descending order of CR across the ESs. Such irregular patterns explain the random rate of CR for PE over achieving the skill of CPRVR. It also identifies that phase E reserves a low level of change in variability for MO as compared to phase B, phase C and phase D. Furthermore, the four distinctive decreases in PE's slopes of progress were observed across 2ndES of phase B, 8thES of phase C, and finally 4th ES of phase D. It is reflective of the characteristics of individuals with ASD, where once they are provided with the routine based repetitive strategy and practice to perform the skill, they eventually master it. Additionally, the slopes of progress in phase E generally show less fluctuations around the mean slop FMS as compared to phase B, phase C and phase D. Finally; it is evident that the discrete trial training has been defined as a strategy to teach new skills to children's acquisition of communicative skills, e.g., words and gestures (Prizant et al., 1998).

Conclusion

PE was able to point accompanying stress on the first and last syllables (familiar 'sound of a') of two target words with IR during 90% of opportunities across three consecutive teaching sessions. Mastery for each step was set at 90% correct independent responses during three consecutive teaching periods. Therefore, PE achieved the first task objective, i.e., pointing and stressing the syllable at the higher rate of change during phase E. Likewise, PE was able to point the missing space (a) in two target words of 3 alphabets coordinating with verbal labeling in the missing spaces with IR during 90% of opportunities across three consecutive teaching sessions. Mastery for each step was set at 90% correct independent responses during three consecutive teaching periods. Therefore, PE achieved the second task objective, i.e., coordinate pointing with verbal labeling at the higher rate of change during phase E. Similarly, PE was able to write counting in blanks on turn immediately after conversational/communicative partner with IR during 90% of opportunities across three consecutive teaching sessions. Mastery for each step is set at 90% correct independent responses during three consecutive teaching

periods. Therefore, PE achieved the third task objective, i.e., coordinate pointing with reciprocal verbal labeling at the higher rate of change during phase E. PE was able to coordinate proximity of 3 steps (without line) with reciprocal verbal respond over alphabets during 90% of opportunities across three consecutive teaching sessions. Mastery for each step is set at 90% correct independent responses during three consecutive teaching periods. Therefore, PE achieved the fourth task, i.e., coordinating proximity with reciprocal verbal respond PE at the higher rate of change during phase E. The researchers concluded that all the task objectives of the present study were developed at a higher rate of change during phase E.

Recommendations

The researchers recommended that the Government of Punjab provide the context of phase E i.e. autism friendly training rooms and trained special educationists to individuals with ASD inside the premises of their institutions to benefit from the DTT intervention program.

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